

FACTORS AFFECTING BRAND EQUITY: A STUDY IN PROPERTY ADVERTISING

Ilham¹, R M Permana¹

¹Master of Marketing Management, Trisakti University, Jakarta, Indonesia
r_mersandro@yahoo.com

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to determine the factors that affect brand equity. Some previous studies explain that these factors are television advertising, advertising awareness, brand loyalty, brand image and brand awareness. This study used hypothesis testing methodology. The data was obtained from questionnaire of which the number of variables was 6 items, the number of indicators was 23 items, and the number of respondents selected was 150 people. This empirical study used Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) for the data analysis. The findings in this study were in line with some previous studies.

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1. Introduction

Television has a larger viewer potential. Almost no cost incurred by someone to watch television. Therefore, in general, Indonesian television viewers tend to choose to consume television media, compared to other media. Indonesian population of more than two hundred million people with the population in the regions able to afford viewing television reached 175.296. This figure is certainly a good land for producers to promote their products through television. Television is often considered to be a promotional medium that produces a strong influence on the target. Compared to other promotional media such as newspapers, magazines or radio. Television is the most effective medium to convey information or commercial messages in terms of one of its advantages, namely its ability in reaching a very broad target audience. In addition, television is also capable of generating a very strong impact on consumers through a combination of motion pictures and sound. Brand Equity is one of the most important concepts in the science of marketing, and has been recognized as one of the most valuable intangible assets by most companies (Erenkol and Duygun, 2010). Brand equity is additional utility and value with products or services by brand name (Marinova et al, 2011). High brand equity can cause customers to give positive or strong associations; acquire or increase their cash flow for business, and make product differentiation leading to competitive advantage (Marinova et al, 2011).

Through advertising, the company as a communicator convey a message to the communicant either a message about a product, usefulness, or other important information. One of the fastest growing advertising media is television. The object of the study in this study is METRO TV which is the first 24 hours news television in Indonesia. METRO TV consists of 70% of the news, which is aired in 3 languages, namely Indonesia, English, and Mandarin, plus 30% non educative news programs. METRO TV can be terrestrially captured in 280 cities spread in Indonesian homeland which is transmitted from 52 transmissions. To test the variables affecting brand equity and variables influenced by the brand equity of a product, then the study conducted with sample of a private television viewer in Indonesia. The study was conducted in 2017.

The results of this study is expected to be a material thought to add insight into the Advertising, especially for electronic media advertising such as television advertising. In addition, advertisers are expected to have a reference in making the right decision and effective in order to introduce the product to the target to strengthen the brand.

2. Literature Review

Advertising Television can create long-term brand image for the product (service) or trigger quick sales (Keller, 2016). As a result, based on past study (Huang and Sarigöllü, 2011), it is argued that, advertising can create and improve brand identity by exposing the brand to customers, as well as reinforcing the possibility of being included in the consumer mindset, thus improving the brand's performance. Based on the opinions above, hypotheses are made as follows:

H1 : There is a positive influence of television advertising on brand loyalty.

H2 : There is a positive influence of television advertising on brand awareness.

H3 : There is a positive influence of television advertising on brand equity.

Advertising awareness learns the concept of how consumers engage the website and can improve the effectiveness of advertising. For brands, Keller (2016) define advertising as a form of payment for non-personal presentations and the promotion of ideas, goods or services through mass media such as newspapers, magazines, television or radio by identified sponsors. Based on the opinions above, hypotheses are made as follows:

H4 : There is a positive influence of advertising awareness on brand awareness.

H5 : There is a positive influence of advertising awareness on brand image.

H6 : There is a positive influence of advertising awareness on brand equity.

Brand loyalty differs from other brand equity dimensions, as it is related to usage experience (Salelaw et al, 2015). In addition, brand loyalty reduces uncertainty as well as saves the cost of seeking new relational exchanges with other brands (Erenkol and Duygun, 2010). Brand loyalty makes consumers buy brands regularly and refuse to switch to other competing brands. As a result, brand loyalty is a concept that emphasizes the company, as it can create or retain long-term customer patrons (Marshall, 2015), thereby increasing brand equity. Based on the opinion, hypothesis is made as follows:

H7 : There is a positive influence of brand loyalty on brand equity.

Brand awareness influences consumers in decision making in various ways. When consumers recognize a particular brand, they tend to include names that are on their personal consideration set (Salelaw et al., 2015). It helps consumers to understand the products or services belonging to certain brand categories and what products and services are sold under the brand name (De Matos and Rossi, 2008). Therefore, marketers should concentrate on the right brand management and tactics to build and retain customers by improving relationships between products and customers, thereby affecting the choice of brand customers (Xu and Chen, 2010). Based on the opinions above, hypotheses are made as follows:

H8 : There is a positive influence of brand awareness on brand equity.

H9 : There is a positive influence of brand awareness on brand image.

It is a concept created by consumers for their subjective reasons and personal emotions. The definition of Tjiptono (2015) states that the brand image is the decryption of association and consumer confidence in a particular brand. Alhaddad (2015) define brand image as a set of beliefs possessed about a particular brand. In this case, Confidence plays an important role in the buying decision process when the customer evaluates the selected brand alternatives. Keller in Wu et al.

(2011) defines the image as the total value of the existing societal elements in memoricons that lead to brand perceptions.

H10 : There is a positive influence of brand image on brand equity.

3. Methods

All variables in this study have been tested by using the validity test and reliability test. A description of the validity test and reliability test of this study can be shown in Table 1 below:

Table 1. Validity and Reliability Test.

Variable	Validity Test				Reliability Test		
	N	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	r-tabel	Decision	Item/Statement	Cronbach's Alpha	Decision
Advertising Awareness	150	0,500 – 0,500	0,500	Valid	2	0,926	Reliable
Television Advertising	150	0,588 – 0,692	0,500	Valid	4	0,778	Reliable
Brand Awareness	150	0,796 – 0,909	0,500	Valid	4	0,905	Reliable
Brand Image	150	0,789 – 0,873	0,500	Valid	5	0,919	Reliable
Brand Loyalty	150	0,718 – 0,811	0,500	Valid	4	0,870	Reliable
Brand Equity	150	0,778 – 0,889	0,500	Valid	4	0,852	Reliable

The method used in this study was hypothesis testing, where this method tested the hypotheses, in this case, the effect that occurred in each variable in the hypotheses (Sekaran, 2004). A description of the conceptual model of this study can be shown in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1. Conceptual Model.

This study used SEM (Structural Equation Model) analysis method which was run by using AMOS program (Analysis of Moment Structures) version 21. Path diagram in this study can be seen in Figure 2 below:

Figure 2. Path Diagram.

4. Results

From the results of data processing that has been done on the variables in this study, namely television advertising, advertising awareness, brand loyalty, brand image, brand awareness of brand equity in Property ads on Metro TV, it can be known the SEM model estimation results, shown in the Table 2 below:

Table 2. Estimation Result of SEM Model.

Hypotheses	Relationship	Estimate	C.R.	P-value	Conclusion
H1	Television Advertising → Brand Loyalty	0.253	1,878	0,060	Was not supported
H2	Television Advertising → Brand Awareness	0.496	4,433	0,000	Was supported
H3	Television Advertising → Brand Equity	0,223	2,021	0,043	Was supported
H4	Advertising Awareness → Brand Awareness	0,121	2,051	0,040	Was supported
H5	Advertising Awareness → Brand Image	0,479	7,287	0,000	Was supported
H6	Advertising Awareness → Brand Equity	0,189	2,027	0,043	Was supported
H7	Brand Loyalty → Brand Equity	0,238	2,005	0,045	Was supported
H8	Brand Awareness → Brand Equity	0,315	4,094	0,000	Was supported

H9	Brand Awareness	→ Brand Image	0,276	2,015	0,044	Was supported
H10	Brand Image	→ Brand Equity	0,121	2,051	0,040	Was supported

5. Discussion

The results of study on H1 show that television advertising does not increase brand loyalty. This happens because the television advertising offered is not attractive, or people will still buy even without the television advertising. The results of this study support the results of study that has been done by Salelaw et al. (2015) which in his study concluded that there is no significant influence between television advertising against brand loyalty.

The results of study on H2 support the results of study that has been done by Salelaw et al. (2015) which in his study concluded that there is a significant influence between television advertising and brand awareness.

The results of study on H3 show that television advertising will increase equity to a brand. The results of this study support the results of study that has been done by Zohoori (2013) where in his study concluded that there is significant influence between television advertising and brand equity.

The result of the study on H4 shows that the advertising awareness will increase brand awareness. The results of this study support the results of study that has been done by Alhaddad (2015) which in his study concluded that there is a significant influence between advertising awareness and brand awareness.

The results of the study on H5 show that brand awareness helps to improve the image of a brand. The results of this study support the results of study that has been done by Alhaddad (2015) which in his study concluded that there is a significant influence between brand awareness and brand image.

Results of study on H6 indicate that advertising awareness will increase brand equity. The results of this study support the results of study that has been done by Alhaddad (2015) which in his study concluded that there is a significant influence between advertising awareness and brand equity.

The results of study on H7 indicate that brand loyalty will increase brand equity. The results of this study support the results of study that has been done by Alhaddad (2015) which in his study concluded that there is a significant influence between brand loyalty and brand equity.

The results of study on H8 show that brand awareness will increase the equity of a brand. The results of this study do not support the results of study that has been done by Alhaddad (2015) which in his study concluded that there is a significant influence between brand awareness and brand equity.

The results of the study on H9 show that brand awareness will improve the brand image for the product. The results of this study support the results of study that has been done by Alhaddad (2015) which in his study concluded that there is a significant influence between brand awareness and brand image.

The results of study on H10 show that brand image will increase brand equity for the product. The results of this study support the results of study that has been done by Alhaddad (2015) which in his study concluded that there is a significant influence between brand image and brand equity.

6. Conclusion

Based on the discussion above, we could conclude that factors affecting brand equity in Property Advertising were television advertising, advertising awareness, brand loyalty, brand image and brand awareness. This reinforced some previous studies.

References

- [1] Alhaddad A 2015 *The effect of brand image and brand loyalty on brand equity International Journal of Business and Management Invention.* **3** 28–32
- [2] De Matos C A and Rossi C A V 2008 *Word-of-mouth communications in marketing: a meta-analytic review of the antecedents and moderators.* **36** 578–596
- [3] Erenkol A D and Duygun A 2010 *Customers perceived brand equity and a study on the customers of Bellona which is a Turkish furniture brand.* **16** 93–110
- [4] Huang R and Sarigöllü E 2012 *How brand awareness relates to market outcome brand equity, and the marketing mix.* **65** 92–99
- [5] Keller K L 2016 *Strategic Brand Management, Building, Measuring and Managing Brand Equity* (New Jersey: Prentice Hall, Englewood Cliffs)
- [6] Marinova S, Cui J, Marinov M and Shiu E 2011 *Customers relationship and brand equity: A study of bank retailing in China* ed WBC Poznan pp 6–9
- [7] Marshall C 2015 *The Guardian* (Retrieved: January 29th 2016)
- [8] Salelaw, Tibebe G and Singh A 2015 *The Effect of Advertising Spending and Event Sponsorship on Brand Equity in The Ethiopian Brewery Industry.* **3** 47–68
- [9] Sekaran U 2004 *Study Methods For Business: A Skill Building Approach* 4th Ed. (New York: John Wiley and Sons, Inc.)
- [10] Tjiptono F 2015 *Brand Management & Strategy* (Yogyakarta: Andi Publisher)
- [11] Wu P C S, Yeh G Y and Hsiao C R 2011 *The effect of store image and service quality on brand image and purchase intention for private label brands.* **19** 30–39
- [12] Xu J B and Chen A 2010 *A conceptual framework of hotel experience and customers based brand equity: Some study questions and implications.* **22** 174–193
- [13] Noorjaya M Y and Rahman Z A 2011 *Does Family and Viral Marketing Have Any Effect on Brand Equity.* **1** 1–13
- [14] Zohoori M 2013 *Advertisement and Brand Equity in Fast Food industry of Iran.* **5** 485–494

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